

MIXED MODE FREE-EDGE DELAMINATION IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

A great number of papers on free-edge delamination have been reported to explain the influence of the interlaminar normal stress, σ_z and shear stress, τ_{xz} and their singularity. However, little attention has been paid to the contribution of interlaminar shear stress, τ_{yz} for the delamination problem because the component of τ_{yz} is zero at the free-edge to satisfy the traction-free condition. In this paper, several types of composite laminates such as $[\pm\theta_4/90_4]_s$, $[(\pm\theta_2)_2/90_4]_s$ and $[(\pm\theta)_4/90_4]_s$ are considered to demonstrate the effect of interlaminar shear stresses, τ_{yz} and τ_{xz} , on free-edge delamination. Delamination tests are conducted under uniaxial compression and the experimental results are discussed with the analyzed results by a quasi-three-dimensional finite element method. It is found out that the component of τ_{yz} plays an important role in free-edge delamination and the fracture surfaces between mode II and III delaminations show differences in the slant angle of hackles.

KEYWORDS: Delamination; Fracture Surface; Interlaminar Stress; Mixed Mode; Stacking Sequence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Free-edge delamination in composite laminates results directly from the interlaminar stresses which exist in ply-interfaces and the free-edge. Since delamination reduces the performance of composite structures, numerous investigators have been dealing with the free-edge problem in composite laminates under uniaxial load as shown in figure 1 [1-10].

Most reported studies about the free-edge problem aimed to examine the effect of σ_z and τ_{xz} [1-5]. Interlaminar stresses depend on fiber orientations and stacking sequences. For a laminate consisting of same plies, the magnitude of interlaminar stresses can be changed by stacking sequences. Also, some stacking sequences give tensile σ_z which promotes delamination and

others give compressive σ_z which suppresses delamination. The components of σ_z and τ_{xz} have steep stress gradient near the free-edge, and cause mode I and III delamination, respectively.

Few literatures reported the effect of τ_{yz} on delamination because the stress component is zero at the free-edge to satisfy traction-free condition. In references [6, 7], it was presumed that the component of τ_{yz} also contributed to free-edge delamination. In references [8, 9], mixed mode, mode I and II, fracture analysis was conducted and the results were compared with experimental results. However, they have not clearly discussed the effect of τ_{yz} because the components of σ_z and τ_{yz} were combined and many transverse cracks were correlated with free-edge delamination. Therefore, it is still questionable that the component of τ_{yz} which is zero at the free-edge can cause free-edge delamination individually.

This paper presents the results of an investigation of the contribution of τ_{yz} to free-edge delamination. Delamination tests are conducted under compressive load to eliminate the effect of transverse cracking on delamination. Test specimens are selected to produce compressive σ_z and different magnitude of the ratios of τ_{yz} and τ_{xz} . The mixed ratios of interlaminar shear stresses are controlled by stacking sequences. The laminates are $[\pm\theta_4/90_4]_S$, $[(\pm\theta_2)_2/90_4]_S$ and $[(\pm\theta)_4/90_4]_S$, where θ is 30° and 45° . The analysis of specimens is performed by a quasi-three-dimensional finite element method and the experimental results are discussed with the analytical results. Finally, the characteristics of delamination fracture surfaces are examined by a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

2. TEST SPECIMENS

2.1 Specimen Design The relation between in-plane stresses and interlaminar stresses is utilized to determine test specimens. When a laminate is subjected to uniaxial strain as shown in figure 1, all components of stresses are only function of y and z . The sign and magnitude of the components of interlaminar stresses at an arbitrary interface, $z=z_k$, can be estimated by the components of in-plane stresses which can be calculated by classical laminate theory (CLT) [10].

$$(\sigma_z)_{\text{at the free-edge of } z=z_k} \propto M_y(z_k) = \frac{1}{h^2} \int_{z_k}^h \sigma_y(0, z) z \, dz \quad (1)$$

$$(\tau_{yz})_{\text{maximum of } z=z_k} \propto N_y(z_k) = \frac{1}{h} \int_{z_k}^h \sigma_y(0, z) \, dz \quad (2)$$

$$(\tau_{xz})_{\text{at the free-edge of } z=z_k} \propto N_{xy}(z_k) = -\frac{1}{h} \int_{z_k}^h \tau_{xy}(0, z) \, dz \quad (3)$$

In the equations, h is one half of the thickness. M_y and N_y represent the normalized values of induced moment and resultant force of σ_y , respectively. N_{xy} represents the normalized value of resultant force of τ_{xy} .

In order to generate compressive σ_z under compressive load which eliminates the effect of

transverse cracking and control the ratios of τ_{yz} and τ_{xz} , $[\pm\theta_4/90_4]_S$, $[(\pm\theta_2)_2/90_4]_S$ and $[(\pm\theta)_4/90_4]_S$ stackings are chosen. Then θ is selected as 30° and 45° considering the general usage of laminates.

2.2 Analysis of Specimens A quasi-three-dimensional FEM is utilized for the analysis of specimens. The theoretical bases are similar to the model reported in reference [3]. For the analysis, eight node isoparametric elements with three degrees of freedom per node are utilized and one quarter of the laminate is modeled as shown in figure 1. The ratio of thickness and width, $2h/2b$, is $1/4$ and each ply is modeled with one element through its thickness. This model has 633 nodes and 192 elements for all specimens. The material used in this study is TORAYCA P3051 graphite/epoxy and the mechanical properties are given in table 1.

Figure 2 shows the deformed shape of $[(\pm 45)_4/90_4]_S$ laminate on the y-z plane when $\epsilon_x = -0.1$. All specimens show similar deformation on the plane. Because of the mismatch of Poisson's ratio between $\pm\theta^\circ$ and 90° plies, and the condition of perfect bonding of plies, the free-edge region of the specimens shrinks in the z-direction. Therefore, σ_z may be compressive near the free-edge, and τ_{yz} may be maximum at the $-\theta/90$ interface.

Figure 3 and 4 show the distributions of interlaminar stresses along each interface of $[(\pm 45)_4/90_4]_S$ laminate when $\epsilon_x = -1.0$. For all the specimens, the shapes of the distributions of σ_z and τ_{yz} are very similar to the distributions shown in figure 3. σ_z is compressive near the free-edge of the interfaces between $z=0$ and $4t$, and the magnitude of σ_z is negligibly small between $z=5t$ and $11t$, where t represents one ply thickness. The maximum magnitude of τ_{yz} occurs at the $-\theta/90$ interface, $z=4t$. As shown in figure 3-(c) and 4, the magnitude of τ_{xz} at the θ/θ interfaces is greatest in $[\pm\theta_4/90_4]_S$ laminate and smallest in $[(\pm\theta)_4/90_4]_S$ laminate.

3. EXPERIMENT

Delamination tests under compressive load are conducted on six types of laminates, $[\pm\theta_4/90_4]_S$, $[(\pm\theta_2)_2/90_4]_S$ and $[(\pm\theta)_4/90_4]_S$, where θ is 30° and 45° . The laminates are fabricated in a panel autoclave according to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. The fiber volume fraction is determined to be approximately 70 percent and total thickness to be 2.8 mm after cure. Test specimens are 180 mm long and 20 mm wide. The gage length is 105 mm.

All specimens are tested on an Instron testing machine. The speed of testing is set to affect a constant strain rate of 0.005 mm/mm-min in the gage section. To prevent buckling of the specimens subjected to compressive load, a pair of side support devices are employed. The length of the side support device is 101.6 mm.

During the delamination test, load versus deformation curve is continuously plotted by an X-Y recorder. As soon as a pop-in is detected in the load versus deformation curve with an audible sound, the specimen is unloaded. The free-edges of the specimen are then subjected to microscopic examination. Free-edge delaminations are observed in all specimens after the first pop-in with a sound. The fracture surfaces of delamination are further examined by SEM for the determination of delamination modes.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Test results are summarized in table 2. The locations of free-edge delamination are indicated by arrows and given in the parentheses. The delamination onset stresses are calculated from the pop-in points of load versus deformation curves. Based on CLT and quadratic failure criterion [11], the estimated stresses at the onset of first ply failure (FPF) are -471 MPa for $(\pm 30/90)$ laminate family and -284 MPa for $(\pm 45/90)$ laminate family. In both laminates, the FPF is estimated to occur at the $\pm\theta$ plies.

$[(\pm\theta)_4/90_4]_S$ laminate is delaminated at the $-\theta/90$ interface ($z=4t$). When θ is 30° , six specimens are tested and five specimens are failed with extensive delamination at the $-30/90$ interface. In a specimen, however, only free-edge delamination is observed at the $-30/90$ interface. From these results, it is presumed that the failure follows after the free-edge delamination. When θ is 45° , delamination is observed at the $-45/90$ interface without laminate failure. It is found out to be a mode II free-edge delamination induced by τ_{yz} because the component of σ_z is compressive and the magnitude of τ_{xz} is negligible as shown in figure 3. In this case, the possibility of crack initiation at the interior region slightly away from the free-edge rather than right at the free-edge should be further examined.

In $[\pm\theta_4/90_4]_S$ laminate, delamination is observed at the θ/θ interface, $z=8t$. The distributions of interlaminar stresses along $z/h=0.67$ in figure 3-(a), (b) and 4-(a) show that the effect of τ_{xz} is predominant on the delamination. The laminate has lowest delamination onset stress as shown in table 2.

In $[(\pm 30_2)_2/90_4]_S$ laminate, all specimens are failed with the extensive delamination at the inner $30/30$ interface, $z=6t$. In $[(\pm 45_2)_2/90_4]_S$ laminate, delaminations are observed at the inner $45/45$ interface, $z=6t$, and at the $-45/90$ interface, $z=4t$. In $[(\pm\theta_2)_2/90_4]_S$ laminate, the magnitude of τ_{xz} at the outer θ/θ interface, $z=10t$, and that at the inner θ/θ interface, $z=6t$, are nearly the same. However, the magnitude of τ_{yz} at the inner θ/θ interface is higher than that at the outer θ/θ interface. Therefore, the inner θ/θ interface is more prone to delaminate than the outer θ/θ interface. The test results on $[(\pm\theta_2)_2/90_4]_S$ laminate give information that the effect of τ_{yz} on free-edge delamination is slightly greater when θ is 45° than 30° , and the effect of τ_{xz} is slightly greater when θ is 30° than 45° .

Now the failure surfaces of free-edge delamination will be discussed. Figure 5 shows typical fracture surfaces, 5-(a) for the $-45/90$ interface of $[(\pm 45)_4/90_4]_S$ laminate, 5-(b) for the inner $45/45$ interface of $[(\pm 45_2)_2/90_4]_S$ laminate, and 5-(c) for the $45/45$ interface of $[\pm 45_4/90_4]_S$ laminate. The extensive hackles (lacerations and serrations) in the surfaces are clear evidence that the delaminations are created by interlaminar shear stresses. It is reported that the hackles always tend to align more or less perpendicular to the fiber imprints or uncovered fibers [12]. However, a closer inspection of the slant angle of hackles shows differences between the modes of free-edge delamination. The slant angle of hackles is depicted in figure 6. In the figure, the lines AA' represent the perpendicular line with respect to the fibers of fiber imprints. As shown in figure 5-(a) and sketched in figure 6-(a), the hackles formed by the predominant effect of τ_{yz} tend to align normal to y axis. As shown in figure 5-(c) and sketched in figure

6-(b) the hackles formed by the predominant effect of τ_{xz} tend to align normal to x axis. From above results and figure 5-(b), the fracture surface of the inner 45/-45 interface of $[(\pm 45)_2/90_4]_s$ laminate, it is inferred that τ_{yz} has predominant effect on the delamination.

5. CONCLUSION

The analytical and experimental results on $[\pm\theta_4/90_4]_s$, $[(\pm\theta_2)_2/90_4]_s$ and $[(\pm\theta)_4/90_4]_s$, where θ is 30° and 45° , under uniaxial compression show that the contribution of τ_{yz} increases as the magnitude of τ_{xz} decreases by an alternating sequence of $\pm\theta$ plies. $[(\pm\theta)_4/90_4]_s$ laminate exhibits mode II delamination at the $-\theta/90$ interface due to the contribution of τ_{yz} which is zero at the free-edge. $[\pm\theta_4/90_4]_s$ laminate exhibits mode III delamination at the θ/θ interface due to the predominant effect of τ_{xz} . $[(\pm\theta_2)_2/90_4]_s$ laminate exhibits mixed mode delamination at the inner θ/θ interface due to the combined effect of τ_{yz} and τ_{xz} . When the effect of τ_{yz} is predominant on free-edge delamination, the possibility of crack initiation at the region slightly away from the free-edge should be further examined. The fracture surfaces of three types of delamination modes show differences in the direction of hackles in between uncovered fibers or fiber imprints. The tips of hackles tend to align normal to the direction of relative motion of the adjacent ply.

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8. BIOGRAPHY

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Dr. D. M. Kim received Ph.D degree (1991) from KAIST. The title of his thesis is "Free-Edge Delamination in Advanced Composite Laminates". He dealt with various free-edge problems such as mode II free-edge delamination, a simple stacking method for thick laminate to suppress delamination and the mechanism of free-edge damage progression in thick laminates under compression-compression fatigue.

Table 1 Material properties of TORAYCA P3051 graphite/epoxy

$E_{11} = 127.8$ (GPa),	$E_{22} = E_{33} = 9.4$ (GPa)
$G_{12} = G_{13} = 4.2$ (GPa),	$G_{23} = 3.1$ (GPa)
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.28$,	$\nu_{23} = 0.52$
$Z = 61$ (MPa),	$Z' = 141$ (MPa)
$S = 69$ (MPa)	

Z, Z' : interlaminar tensile and compressive strength

S : interlaminar shear strength

Table 2 Delamination locations and onset stresses in MPa

Laminate	Location	$\bar{\sigma}_{del}$
$[\pm 30_4/90_4]_s$	30 ₄ /-30 ₄ /90 ₄ (8t) ↑	-156.7
$[(\pm 30_2)_2/90_4]_s$	±30 ₂ /30 ₂ /-30 ₂ /90 ₄ (6t) ↑	-292.9
$[(\pm 30)_4/90_4]_s$	(±30) ₄ /90 ₄ (4t) ↑	-341.4
$[\pm 45_4/90_4]_s$	45 ₄ /-45 ₄ /90 ₄ (8t) ↑	-147.0
$[(\pm 45_2)_2/90_4]_s$	±45 ₂ /45 ₂ /-45 ₂ /90 ₄ (4t, 6t) ↑	-194.5
$[(\pm 45)_4/90_4]_s$	(±45) ₄ /90 ₄ (4t) ↑	-196.3

Figure 1 Laminate geometry and delamination modes.

Figure 2 Deformed shape of $[(\pm 45)_4/90_4]_8$ laminate on y-z plane ($\epsilon_x = -0.1$).

(a) σ_z

(b) τ_{yz}

(c) τ_{xz}

(a) $[\pm 45_4/90_4]_s$

(b) $[(\pm 45_2)_2/90_4]_s$

Figure 4 Distributions of τ_{xz} in $[\pm 45_4/90_4]_s$ and $[(\pm 45_2)_2/90_4]_s$ laminates ($\epsilon_x = -1.0$).

Figure 3 Distributions of interlaminar stresses in $[\pm 45_4/90_4]_s$ laminate ($\epsilon_x = -1.0$).

(a) -45/90 interface of $[(\pm 45)_4/90_4]_s$

(b) inner 45/-45 interface of $[(\pm 45)_2/90_4]_s$

(c) 45/-45 interface of $[\pm 45_4/90_4]_s$

Figure 5 SEM photographs of typical fracture surfaces for $(\pm 45/90)$ laminate family.

(a) Mode II delamination (b) Mode III delamination

Figure 6 Sketches of slant angle of hackles in between fibers.